

THEIA^{XR} NEWSLETTER

ISSUE No. 5

UPDATE ON THEIA^{XR}

Summertime has come and we are very pleased to introduce to you the 5th edition of our project newsletter. Slowly, but steadily we are approaching the end of the THEIA^{XR} project so we can offer you with this issue lots of exciting events, conferences and meetings we have had in the last few months. The next, and sadly final, few months will be dominated by dissemination and exploitation activities which Gerald Fritz-Mayer, technical project and exploitation manager, will tell you more about.

Gerald Fritz-Mayer, THEIA^{XR} technical project and exploitation manager states:

“The last project months have been picked with exploitation activities in various highly relevant industrial domains fostering the awareness of THEIA^{XR}’s results in a larger group of stakeholders. In addition, great efforts have been put into challenging question on ethics and privacy that emerge from the technological advances for workplaces and society. During the second half of the project a lot of technical achievements have been developed into innovative solutions and services

which will be exploited as key results of the THEIA^{XR} project. The project partners are currently working on transforming these outcomes towards sustainable business opportunities, plans for further exploitation, as well as joint activities beyond the project duration.”

THEIA^{XR} @ CONFERENCES AND TRADE FAIRS

INTERALPIN

From May 6th till May 9th 2025, the [INTERALPIN](#), the leading international trade fair for alpine technologies and a central meeting point for industry, took place in Innsbruck, Austria. Partner [Prinoth AG](#) is one of the main exhibitors at the trade fair and enabled the consortium to demonstrate concepts of the snow grooming use case.

The demonstrator consisted of a complete snow groomer cabin, equipped with a selection of eXtended Reality technologies. Combined with a virtual world representing a skiing resort ([Creanex](#)), the demonstrator provided people with the possibility to virtually drive a snow groomer through the environment. Additionally, the eXtended Reality technologies enabled users to see invisible information in their field-of-view,

like skiers coming down the slopes in angles not visible to the users. Furthermore, laser projections within the environment, providing directions to the operators, potentially in difficult situations like e.g., fog, snowstorms, etc., to aid them in fulfilling their tasks or bringing them home safely. The demonstrator attracted a large crowd of people, not only snow groomer operators and technology developers, but also children, managers and general audience. We received very valuable and interesting feedback on our presented solutions. Statements varying from *“This is such a cool solution!”* up to *“Why would I need this kind of technology?”* highlighted the different approaches people currently have towards eXtended Reality solutions.

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Figure 1: Impressions from the THEIA^{XR} booth at the INTERALPIN

Additionally, our partners from [University of Luxembourg](#) and [Hochschule der Medien](#) used this possibility to interact with many operators of snow groomers. Not only did we collect feedback on the functionality of the eXtended Reality technologies, but we also focused on gathering input on social aspects, like usability, added-value and ethics on the usage of eXtended Reality in their daily job. The INTERALPIN trade fair has proven to be a huge source of knowledge, and we extensively interviewed a large collection of operators and received a large amount of feedback also on our social and ethical research topics.

Figure 2: The demonstrator at the INTERALPIN

It was very impressive to see that so many people were interested in our project results and wanted to experience our demonstrator, resulting in many people queuing for almost half an hour to finally test it. Each feedback is a valuable asset for the continuous development within the project.

Figure 3: Sophie Doublet (UL), Matias Laakso (CREA), Daniel Röck (PRIN), Anastasia Sergeeva (UL) and Martijn Rooker (TTC) in front of the demonstrator

Finally, a huge thanks goes out in the first place to [Prinoth AG](#), for offering the THEIA^{XR} consortium the possibility to demonstrate these results at such an amazing trade fair and getting us in contact with so many high qualified people that have contributed to our research. Secondly, many thanks go out to the partners [Technical University of Dresden](#), [Technical University Graz](#), [TTControl GmbH](#), [Haption](#), [Creanex](#), [University of Luxembourg](#) and [Hochschule der Medien](#) who have worked very hard in cooperation with Prinoth to make this demonstrator a reality. This excellent collaboration is required to make projects like THEIA^{XR} a huge success!

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bauma 2025

We are looking back to an incredible [bauma](#) with great THEIA^{XR} representation.

Figure 4: The demonstrator at the bauma (Volker Waurich, TUD left, Martijn Rooker, TTC right)

A special highlight was the bauma Innovation Award ceremony, where our project [THEIA^{XR}](#) was honoured with a nomination as one of the finalists for the extended excavator HMI, a great appreciation for the hard work. Congrats to the colleagues from [Technische Universität Dresden](#) & [Professur für Baumaschinen Technisches Design | td](#) for this success!

Figure 5: Details at the THEIA^{XR} booth

The conference offered many exciting booths and inspiring presentations at the bauma forum. THEIA^{XR} was further presented at the booth of the coordinator [TTControl](#) with great exchange with the large numbers of visitors.

Figure 6: TTC booth at the bauma

THEIA^{XR} at the iVT Expo

At the iVT in 2023, we started the outreach of our project at a larger scale and many interesting discussions took place presenting our first thoughts and plans for development. Two years later, we had the honour to present the work achieved so far and again, it was an excellent room for exchange of thoughts. The expo was also a great opportunity to discuss THEIA^{XR} results at the stands of [TTControl](#) and [Creanex](#).

Figure 7: Martijn Rooker, TTC, during his presentation

FIELD STUDIES AND WORKSHOPS

THEIA^{XR} workshop on ethical and privacy topics

On the 15th of April, we had the honour to host a workshop titled "Beyond Just Privacy: Addressing Ethical Questions in XR Spaces (EU Projects Experiences)" in the UserLab of the [University of Luxembourg](#). This is part of our work in [THEIA^{XR}](#) on developing Ethical and Privacy Guidelines for XR in the off-highway machinery domain. The goal of the workshop was to align with the expertise of our sister projects [DIDYMOS-XR Project](#), [SUNxr.he](#) and [Sharespace.eu](#) - active as of the same Horizon call. In all these projects, ethics and privacy are treated with great importance: not just as background concerns, but as key factors that form the entire process of technological development. We were also fortunate to have on board a project that places ethics at the core of its efforts through the development of the Code of Conduct of Immersive Technologies -

populations and ensure that those we consider as primary users are not left behind? What should we do if people are afraid of our technologies or are reluctant to participate in our studies?

- How do we navigate high-risk scenarios (like in off-road heavy tech or medical devices)? How can we balance auditability with privacy?
- How can we use the right metaphors or mediums to help technology developers understand ethical concerns the way we do?
- How to address ethically problematic "grey areas": practices that may be legally "ok", but are ethically questionable? What role can legislative efforts play in closing these gaps, and what evidence do legislators need?
- What are the potential adversarial / supportive effects of XR on the future of work, and what role does the calibration of trust play in this equation?

...and much, much more!

Figure 8: THEIA^{XR} ethical and privacy workshop

It was a challenge to coordinate the schedules of so many incredibly busy people, but we made it happen, and the result was a very productive (and intense!) day of discussion. We tackled a range of pressing topics, including:

How can we effectively reach relevant

Figure 9: Project Partners at the workshop

Be sure you don't miss another workshop like that when we will be present at the [EuroXR](#) from September 3rd till 5th in Winterthur, Switzerland.

DO TECH ETHICS (ACTUALLY) WORK?

Author: Anastasia Sergeeva, UL

At the beginning of July 2025, I visited London to take part in a great event provocatively called “Do Tech Ethics (Actually) Work?”, which was organised by my dear friends [Dr. Kathleen Bryson](#) and [Dr. Kathleen Richardson](#) from the [Sharespace.EU](#) project!

For me, it was an excellent opportunity to show the ethics-in-practice challenges we are facing (and overcoming) in the [THEIA^{XR}](#) project, and to connect with more people who understand the role of ethics in all the changes new technologies (AI and XR as two rather bright examples, but certainly not the full list) bring to work and society. I think we ([THEIA^{XR}](#)) are a great example of a project which started by elaborating risks from straightforward topics of privacy and compliance and ended up discussing work ethics and the role of the worker in gaining full-scale control over technology.

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Figure 10: Anastasia at her presentation

Personally, I found the topic of Digital Ethics and the Future of Work to be one of the most intriguing in HCI, as well as in User-centred Privacy research. As current trends show that we are moving towards a rather dystopian future, we can still do things to reverse the process and put more human values into our tech; and it is great to be part of the movement.

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Training Centre in Geradstetten

Author: Manuel Kulzer, HdM

Just as the co-evaluation phase in [THEIA^{XR}](#) is about to kick off, we gained a new partner with the construction training centre Geradstetten. In a visit with my colleague [Tanja](#) last week, team manager Michael Heim and training supervisor Rainer Schif welcomed us to a tour of the facilities, lunch and a chat about the project.

I'm very happy that they agreed we should work together on the upcoming co-evaluation studies, where we definitely want lots of operators, whether trainee or trainer, to get their hands on our prototypes. Thank you for having us, we are looking forward to more visits, interviews and tests!

Figure 11: Picture with the operators in Geradstetten

By the way, behind us in the picture you can see a rather special wheeled Volvo excavator with extendable cabin and quick-change front shield. Very cool. But it could use, for example, a panoramic thermal camera and LED stripes around the windshield for object detection and visualization, so we might need to update.

ÜAZ GLAUCHAU

Also, I just returned from another [THEIA^{XR}](#) co-design trip to the training area of the ÜAZ Glauchau, where I was warmly welcomed by the trainers and incredibly experienced excavator operators Jens and Rocco. They and six of their current apprentices discussed and voted on a total of 14 visionary concepts for positive user experience in the excavator cabin that our team had prepared. We have narrowed down the list to a few really good ones now that can provide joy, stress relief and some very practical value to the operators. More on that hopefully later this summer...

Figure 12: Picture with the Operators in Glauchau

THEIA^{XR} Consortium Meeting No. 5 in Graz

End of June 2025, the [Technical University Graz](#) invited the [THEIA^{XR}](#) project for the 5th consortium meeting.

The meeting started off with many exciting results and news from our use cases. It is a great pleasure to see how the developments and the feedback from the operators are coming together.

For example, after a testing phase, the operators stated that they enjoyed the thermal camera very much, so it was reintegrated into the snow groomer. Another example is the use of icons in addition to colour in our various use cases to guarantee accessibility in our systems for colourblind operators.

Figure 13: Group picture at the general assembly in Graz

In the final phase of the project there will also be a huge focus on dissemination and exploitation. The partners decided to present their results in a harmonized way and to align with a major conference to showcase the results – we are looking forward telling more of it, soon.

We concluded day 1 with a short ethics workshop from the University of Luxembourg.

Figure 14: TUG introduced some of their developments

On the second day, there was some WP1 focus on the organisation of the final review. Subsequently, the WP leads of WP3, WP4 and WP5 presented the latest updates of their work. After lunch, the partners got together in small groups to consolidate on arrangements for the final months of the project and the continuation of their work.

Figure 15: Lots of progress even during coffee breaks

We want to thank the Technical University of Graz once again for hosting this very well-organised consortium meeting. We had a pleasure coming together again and are very much looking forward to our next and final meeting.

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COMING UP

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